

Kinetic Analysis of Thermogravimetric Data of Thorium— All-cis-1,2,3,4-Cyclopentanetetracarboxylic Acid Complex

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Thorium(IV) forms a 1 : 1 complex with all-cis-1, 2,3,4-Cyclopentanetetracarboxylic acid (CPTA). Thermogravimetric analysis indicated that it undergoes primarily a two step decomposition of one corresponding to loss of water and another to the decomposition of the complex. Apparent activation energy, frequency factor and activation entropy were determined. Using the experimental data the reaction order and activation energy were calculated by Freeman-Carroll method and also by Doyle method as modified by J. Zsako, by calculation of standard deviation instead of curve fitting method.

THE rate of thermal decomposition of a complex is determined by the rate at one or more of the stages. In view of the complexity of the decomposition process it is difficult to find a suitable equation to describe the kinetics of all thermal decomposition reactions particularly in the case when kinetics varies during the process. Many methods were developed for deriving kinetic data from thermogravimetric curves.

Freeman-Carroll derived equations for rate processes for non-reversing reactions which may be used for calculating energy of activation and order of reaction from thermogravimetric methods. The trial and error method of Doyle was modified by J. Zsako by introducing the standard deviation instead of curve fitting method for the calculations.

The thermogravimetric data obtained for the second step of decomposition process of Thorium CPTA complex were used for calculating the kinetic parameters viz. energy of activation, entropy, order of reaction and frequency factor which corresponds to the decomposition of complex alone. The first step contributes to the loss of crystallisation water in the complex.

Experimental

Instrument :

A Cahn RG Electrobalance with a Rikedenki Kogyo Co., recorder (Model B 140) operating on 1 mv full scale for obtaining thermogram and Honeywell Brown recorder for obtaining temperature vs time curves were used. A chromel-alumel thermocouple placed 3-4 mm below the sample holder which is a platinum boat 2 mm deep 8 mm diameter was used for recording sample temperature. A 6°/minute heating rate was employed for this work.

Preparation of the sample :

Thorium complex was prepared by mixing equimolar (0.1M) quantities of thorium nitrate and CPTA and raising the pH of the mixture to 3.0 with NH_4OH . The solid thus separated was digested on water bath at 60° for 30 minutes. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water till free from nitrate ion and dried at 100°. The values obtained for the complex are :

C=21.18 ; H=1.96 ; M=45.49 (theoretical)

C=21.01 ; H=1.87 ; M=45.58 (experimental)

which corresponds to a probable formula $\text{Th}(\text{CPTA}) \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; a 1 : 1 metal to ligand complex.

Results and Discussion

The thermogravimetric curve was obtained (using 6°/minute heating rate) up to a temperature of 79J°. At any time the total weight of the sample is measured by the sum of the readings of the potentiometer and chart.

Consider a reaction in a solid state where one product remains in condensed state while another is volatile.

Since the reactions under consideration involve solid state decompositions, Freeman and Carroll gave a relationship which is used to evaluate the reaction kinetics as

$$\frac{-E^*}{2.3 R} \Delta \left(\frac{1}{T} \right) / \Delta \log W_r = -x + \frac{\Delta \log dw/dt}{\Delta \log W_r}$$

where

... (1)

$W_r = W_c - W$ E^* = energy of activation, T = absolute temperature, R = gas constant, W_c = Weight loss at completion of reaction, W = total weight loss up to time, t , x = Order of reaction with respect to A .

Using graphical method $\times$ the intercept and E^* from the slope were calculated as 1.8 and 14.58 K.cal/mol respectively.

The values obtained by above method are compared with the method of Doyle as modified by Zsako.

Doyle's equation for thermogravimetric curves is

$$g(\alpha) = \frac{Z E_a}{Rq} P(x) \quad \dots (2)$$

where $g(\alpha)$ is a certain function of α , where α stands for the fraction of initial compound reacted.

Z = frequency factor, E_a = activation energy, R = gas constant, q = heating rate

$$P(x) \text{ the value of integral } P(x) = \frac{e^{-x}}{x} - \int_x^\infty \frac{e^{-u}}{u} du$$

where $u = E_a/RT$

The main difficulty in this method is that application of the equation as $P(x)$ depends both on temperature and activation energy. Doyle has suggested a trial and error curve fitting method for determination of activation energy. This method was modified by Zsako.

The ratio of the actual weight loss to the total weight loss during the considered step α is the fraction of initial compound reacted in a thermogravimetric step corresponding to a unitary process is given by

$$\alpha = \frac{W_0 - W}{W_0 - W_t} \quad \dots (3)$$

where W , W_0 , W_t are the actual, initial and final weights of the sample respectively.

The value of $g(\alpha)$ was calculated for various values of b in a general equation $\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K(1-\alpha)^b$

$$\dots (4)$$

where 'b' can be considered as apparent reaction order. The values for b taken are $b=0$ or 1 or 2

$$\text{when } b=0 ; g_0(\alpha) = \alpha \quad \dots (5)$$

$$b=1 ; g_1(\alpha) = \ln(1-\alpha) \quad \dots (6)$$

$$b=2 ; g_2(\alpha) = \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \quad \dots (7)$$

If the logarithm of equation (2) is taken

$$\log \frac{Z E_a}{Rq} = \log g(\alpha) - \log P(x) = B \quad \dots (8)$$

The values of the integral

$$P(x) = \frac{e^{-x}}{x} - \int_x^\infty \frac{e^{-u}}{u} du \quad \dots (9)$$

were calculated and tabulated by Doyle for x values covering a range from 10 to 50 and these values were used in calculating 'B' in equation B.

$$B_0 = \log g_0(\alpha) - \log P(x) \quad \dots (10)$$

$$B_1 = \log g_1(\alpha) - \log P(x) \quad \dots (11)$$

$$B_2 = \log g_2(\alpha) - \log P(x) \quad \dots (12)$$

The $-\log P(x)$ values were taken corresponding to over a range of 10 to 22 E_a Value (as E_a value according to graphical method is 14.58 K.cal/mol) and over a temperature range of 280° to 420° (corresponding to temperatures prior to decomposition and to formation of oxide from the complex (Fig. 1).

TEMP.
Fig. 1.

The average of B values as obtained at different values of E_a and at different temperatures was taken and

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{(B_i - \bar{B})^2}{r}} \quad \dots (13)$$

Where B_i is any value, $\bar{B}$ is arithmetical mean, r is number of values

δ values for B_0 , B_1 and B_2 are calculated similarly and given in Table 1.

The δ value is minimum if the apparent order of reaction b is taken as, 2 i.e., 2nd order reaction. Thus from tested b values, $b=2$ is the best.

TABLE I—SAMPLE WT AND LOG $g(\alpha)$ DATA AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	W mg	α	$\log(\alpha)$	$\log\left(\ln\frac{1}{1-\alpha}\right)$	$\log\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$
280	16.98	0.04625	-1.3349	-1.3265	-1.3144
290	16.94	0.05125	-1.2903	-1.2804	-1.2675
300	16.90	0.05624	-1.2499	-1.2386	-1.2249
310	16.89	0.05750	-1.2403	-1.2284	-1.2146
320	16.87	0.06000	-1.2218	-1.2095	-1.1949
330	16.85	0.06250	-1.2041	-1.1896	-1.1760
340	16.78	0.07125	-1.1472	-1.1318	-1.1151
350	16.73	0.07750	-1.1107	-1.0930	-1.0756
360	16.70	0.08108	-1.0911	-1.0725	-1.0543
370	16.65	0.08750	-1.0580	-1.0384	-1.0182
380	16.53	0.10250	-0.9803	-0.9662	-0.9428
390	16.37	0.12250	-0.9119	-0.8540	-0.8551
400	16.05	0.16250	-0.7892	-0.7518	-0.7122
410	15.75	0.20000	-0.6990	-0.6520	-0.6001
420	15.40	0.24370	-0.6131	-0.5545	-0.4919

$W_0 = 17.35$ mg.
 $W_t = 9.35$ mg.

E_a	$b=0$ δ	$b=1$ δ	$b=2$ δ
12	0.008754	0.006068	0.001339
14	0.001576	0.003118	0.0004492
16	0.01076	0.008908	0.006233
18	—	—	0.01249
20	—	—	0.01673

δ has a minimum value for $E_a = 14.0$ K.cal/mol with second order reaction. This corresponds to $\bar{B}_2 = 6.09326$. By means of equation

$$\log Z = \bar{B} + \log Rq - \log E_a \quad \dots (14)$$

the apparent frequency factor $\log Z$ was calculated as 6.0264. The apparent activation entropy was calculated using the equation

$$S^* = 2.303 \log \frac{Zh}{KT}$$

The value for T was taken as the temperature $T_{\frac{1}{2}}$ at which the weight loss is half of the total weight loss in the considered step and $S^* = -15.9$ eu.

The values for apparent reaction order and activation energy calculated by Freeman and Carroll method and Zsako's modified Doyle method are given

	E_a K. Cal/mol	b
Freeman and Carroll	14.58	1.8
Zsako	14.0	2

The values are in good agreement with one another. As the standard deviation δ is a measure of precision between the experimental data and presumed kinetic equation, these values can be considered more reliable than by other methods and can be applied for study of solid state reaction mechanism.

References

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